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Abstract	This document presents the summary of initial results and progress of the task 4.3.

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History of Changes

Version	Date	Reason of change
V0.1 (draft)	20 June 2025	The initial draft of the document is ready and ready for distribution between PERSEPHONE project partners to review.
V0.5	22 July 2025	Updated the report after an internal review
V1.0	30 July 2025	Final version ready

Executive summary

This deliverable, D4.3, presents the progress and outcomes of Task 4.3, which focuses on traversability estimation and risk assessment for autonomous robotic platforms operating in underground mining environments. Given the unpredictable and dynamic nature of these environments, robust terrain understanding is crucial for enabling safe and autonomous navigation.

The work described in this report centers around a series of methods that estimate terrain traversability using LiDAR, RGB, and multi-modal sensory data. These methods are designed to function without reliance on pre-installed infrastructure or prior maps. Multiple complementary approaches are presented: a LiDAR-based geometric traversability analysis, a semantic traversability framework using large-scale vision-language models (VLMs), and a ground segmentation approach based on RGB-LiDAR fusion. These techniques are integrated into the autonomy stack via the STAGE framework, allowing real-time evaluation of terrain safety during mission execution. To enable long-term monitoring and safety assessment, the deliverable also includes a risk assessment pipeline based on repeated scans of the environment, as well as change detection modules that compare current point cloud maps with historical data to identify shifts in terrain structure or potential hazards.

While earlier deliverables such as D4.1 and D4.2 used ground-truth odometry for mapping and navigation, this work lays the groundwork for risk-aware planning that functions based on perception-driven SLAM outputs. These advancements allow robots to reason about where to drive, stop, or avoid, even in the absence of global positioning or communication infrastructure. The deliverable serves as a foundation for field integration and testing in upcoming work packages. All proposed algorithms are developed with real-world deployment in mind and will be validated in field trials scheduled for September 2025 at the GM mine in Athens.

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2 Introduction

Navigating subterranean environments, such as active or abandoned mines, poses significant challenges due to dynamic and unpredictable terrain conditions. These underground spaces are susceptible to hazards like rockfalls, tunnel collapses, water accumulation, and unstable surfaces. Ensuring the safe traversal of autonomous ground or aerial robots in such conditions necessitates robust, real-time terrain assessment mechanisms.

Task 4.3 addresses these concerns by developing an integrated framework that combines online traversability analysis with risk assessment. The objective is to equip autonomous robotic platforms with sensor-driven intelligence capable of understanding terrain characteristics and identifying hazardous zones based on structural changes in the mine environment over time.

This document (D4.3) outlines the methodologies, frameworks, and progress made toward enabling these capabilities, building upon sensor data such as solid-state LiDAR to assess terrain traversability and to monitor topological changes indicating structural risk. The deliverable encapsulates both the geometric and learning-based approaches explored and highlights the simulation-based validation performed in representative mining environments.

Machines Terminology:

- Explorer --> Machine 1 that autonomously explores and maps the unknown environment.
- Deployer --> Machine 2 that oversees autonomously navigating to area of interest (mine face) based on received information from Explorer machine.
- Supplier --> Machine 3 that brings reinforcements and additional robots such as the stinger robot to the mine face ahead of the deployment.

2.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this document is to:

- Present the techniques developed for geometric and semantic traversability analysis using LiDAR-based 2.5D mapping and neural network-based classification of traversable terrain.
- Describe the design and implementation of a change detection-based risk assessment pipeline, capable of identifying and localizing deformations or hazardous structural changes in underground tunnel environments.
- Report the experimental evaluations and simulations conducted to validate these approaches under various realistic mine scenarios, including repeated scans of dynamically altered environments.
- Document the technical integration and testing progress made between project months M12 and M18, as outlined in Task 4.3 of the work package.

This deliverable aims to serve as a comprehensive record of the task's intermediate outcomes and provide the basis for continued integration into autonomous navigation and mapping systems used in underground exploration.

This deliverable covers the development and validation of components under Task 4.3, specifically:

- **Traversability Analysis:**
 - A geometric traversability map using 2.5D grid mapping derived from LiDAR point clouds, incorporating slope, surface roughness, and step height metrics.
 - An environment-agnostic, semantics-driven traversability framework employing neural networks to classify terrain segments into traversable, semi-traversable, or non-traversable categories based on visual and geometric cues.
- **Risk Assessment:**
 - An in-house change detection framework designed to detect local structural deformations in the mine topology between sequential scans.
 - Simulation-based studies that emulate tunnel deformations to validate the detection of collapse-prone or high-risk zones.

The scope excludes final deployment or field trials in operational mine sites, which are planned for future work. It focuses instead on the design, simulation, and intermediate integration of the developed methods within a controlled environment.

2.2 Related documents

This deliverable (D4.3) builds directly upon the autonomy foundations laid out in D4.1 and D4.2, which collectively developed and validated core navigation capabilities for autonomous exploration and routine inspection in subterranean environments.

- D4.1 introduced the STAGE planner a Semantics and Traversability-Aware Graph-Based Exploration framework designed for online autonomous navigation in unknown and unstructured environments such as underground mines. STAGE incrementally builds a local subgraph using semantic cues (e.g., terrain class, obstacle presence) and traversability information (e.g., surface roughness, inclination) to guide the robot efficiently toward global frontiers. This foundational system enables safe and goal-directed exploration during the first-time mapping of unknown mine segments.
- D4.2 expanded upon this by incorporating routine navigation capabilities using global waypoint-based planning. This allowed the robot to revisit

regions of interest such as mine faces, critical junctions, or equipment sites based on a previously built global map. The autonomy layer manages transitions between exploration and inspection modes, ensuring seamless re-navigation even in partially dynamic environments.

The work presented in D4.3 leverages this autonomy framework to enable a complete autonomy pipeline. In particular:

- The traversability estimation techniques introduced in this document both geometric (2.5D grid maps) and semantic (neural network-based terrain classification) are designed to operate in synergy with STAGE, enhancing its ability to reason about terrain suitability in real-time.
- The routine scanning and inspection required for risk assessment is made possible by the robust navigation autonomy established in D4.1 and D4.2. The robot autonomously traverses predefined or previously explored areas, capturing successive LiDAR scans for change detection-based hazard analysis. This feedback loop of perception and risk assessment depends on reliable global path execution, as documented in D4.2, and informed frontier exploration as per D4.1.

Together, these documents form a cohesive stack of capabilities: from autonomous navigation (D4.1, D4.2), to terrain understanding and hazard perception (D4.3), ultimately enabling long-duration autonomous operation in high-risk underground environments.

3 Technical Details

3.1 LiDAR based geometric Traversability analysis

Autonomous navigation in underground mines demands a robust perception system capable of evaluating the traversability of terrain in real-time. This is critical not only for safe path planning and motion execution, but also for enabling higher-level autonomy such as routine inspections, hazard identification, and collaborative exploration. In this task, we have developed a dual-layer traversability analysis framework that integrates geometric terrain assessment using LiDAR-based elevation maps with semantics-aware terrain classification via deep learning. This framework provides a spatially dense, sensor-driven understanding of terrain affordances and feeds directly into the autonomy stack developed in STAGE (D4.1), enabling reliable ground navigation and proactive risk avoidance in complex subterranean settings.

The first component of our traversability framework focuses on analyzing the physical shape and texture of the terrain using data collected from the robot's LiDAR sensor. As the robot moves through the mine, it continuously generates a local elevation map. This map represents the surrounding terrain in a 2.5-dimensional format, essentially capturing the height of the ground surface at each point within a localized area around the robot.

From this elevation map, three main features of the terrain are extracted:

- **Slope:** This tells us how steep the terrain is in each area. Steeper areas are generally harder or riskier for a robot to drive over.
- **Surface Roughness:** This measures how bumpy or uneven the ground is. Highly uneven surfaces may pose a risk to stability or traction.
- **Step Height:** This indicates how much the ground level changes between adjacent areas. For example, a sudden drop or rise in ground level could be interpreted as a step or ledge.

Each of these characteristics is compared against safe operational limits that are specific to the robot's design. For instance, if the slope in a certain area exceeds the maximum angle that the robot can climb without tipping over, that part of the map is marked as non-traversable. Similarly, areas with very rough surfaces or sharp step changes may also be considered risky or impassable.

To evaluate the terrain directly beneath and around the robot, we define a polygon that matches the robot's footprint essentially the area it occupies on the ground. This polygon is projected onto the elevation map, and the terrain characteristics within this area are averaged to produce a single score. This score reflects how safe or easy it is for the robot to move forward in its current direction.

This geometric analysis provides a very detailed, real-time picture of the terrain's physical features and helps the robot make low-level movement decisions, such as choosing whether to stop, steer away, or proceed cautiously.

While geometric information provides a solid foundation for understanding the physical layout of the terrain, it doesn't tell the whole story. For example, a flat surface could either be dry asphalt or a pool of water. Both might look similar in terms of slope or height, but one is perfectly safe to traverse, while the other could be hazardous. To address this, we introduced a second layer of analysis that adds semantic context to the robot's understanding of the environment.

This component uses a deep learning model trained to recognize different types of terrain based on camera images and depth information. The model classifies each area of the ground into one of several categories, including:

- Untraversable terrain such as large rocks, debris, or walls.
- Undesirable terrain like water or ice, which may be slippery or unstable.
- Rough terrain such as gravel or sand, which may be navigable but not ideal.
- Optimal terrain like dry soil or asphalt, which offers safe and efficient traversal.

The classification is further refined using information about the slope of each terrain segment. For example, even if a surface is dry dirt, it may become non-traversable if it's located on a steep incline. The system takes this into account and adjusts the traversability score accordingly. Once the terrain classification and slope information are combined, each pixel in the camera image is assigned a traversability score. These scores are then projected back into the robot's three-dimensional point cloud, effectively labeling every point in space with a value that indicates how safe that area is to traverse. This results in a semantically labeled 3D map of the environment, where each area of interest not only has geometric properties but also a semantic tag and a corresponding traversability rating.

To maintain a consistent and memory-efficient representation, these semantic scores are stored in a 3D volumetric map using a technique that allows fast updates and queries. This map forms the semantic layer of the robot's understanding of the environment and is used by the planner to reason about terrain types during both exploration and route planning.

3.1.1 Integration into the STAGE Autonomy Pipeline:

The two layers of traversability analysis geometric and semantic are tightly integrated into the STAGE autonomy framework. During first-time exploration, the robot relies on these layers to evaluate different areas of the map and select paths that are not only reachable but also safe and efficient to travel. The STAGE planner uses this information to build a global understanding of the mine and to guide the robot toward unexplored areas without taking unnecessary risks.

During repeated inspections or routine navigation, such as returning to a mine face or revisiting key areas for hazard monitoring, the robot again uses the traversability scores to ensure it takes a safe route. This is particularly important in scenarios where the environment may have changed since the last visit for instance, if part of a tunnel has partially collapsed or new debris has appeared.

The traversability framework allows the robot to detect such changes and adjust its path accordingly. Moreover, the traversability information also plays a role in risk assessment and hazard detection. By comparing previously mapped areas to new scans collected during routine missions, the robot can identify changes in terrain or structure. When these changes result in a significant drop in traversability such as a newly formed depression or a shifted rock mass the system flags them as potential hazards. This capability enhances the safety of the robot and supports early warning systems for dangerous areas within the mine.

In summary, this dual layer traversability framework provides the robot with both a physical and contextual understanding of its surroundings. It enables real-time decision-making, improves long-term mission safety, and forms a critical foundation for the complete autonomy stack developed within the project.

Figure 1: Integration of geometric and semantic traversability analysis into the STAGE autonomy planner. (Top row) Geometric traversability map showing safe navigation through green zones and termination of path at a red (non-traversable) area. (Bottom row) Semantic traversability map derived from learned terrain classes and fused depth data. In both cases, the STAGE planner recognizes a blocked region near the tunnel's end and marks the path endpoint with a red sphere to indicate an untraversable frontier. Subfigures (a) provide global context; subfigures (b) highlight the affected frontier region in detail.

The Figure 1 illustrates the integration of both geometric and semantic traversability analysis within the STAGE autonomy pipeline for autonomous navigation in subterranean environments. The top row shows results from the geometric traversability layer, while the bottom row shows results from the semantic traversability layer. In both rows, the subfigure on the left provides a zoomed-out view of the robot's local map and planned path, while the right subfigures offer a closer look at the region near the frontier.

In the geometric map (top row), the robot's navigation is guided through a traversable tunnel segment primarily colored in green, indicating low terrain risk

and high traversability. However, as the robot approaches a red region, which denotes an untraversable zone (likely due to poor terrain characteristics such as steep slope or high roughness), the planner correctly identifies this area as unsuitable for further navigation. As a result, the end of the planned path is marked with a red sphere, symbolizing a non-traversable frontier.

Similarly, in the semantic traversability map (bottom row), the robot uses learned terrain classifications (e.g., optimal, rough, undesirable, untraversable) fused with geometric cues to interpret the environment. Again, the robot follows a semantically validated path toward the frontier. Upon encountering a region that is semantically marked as hazardous or non-traversable (e.g., due to presence of rubble, water, or narrow passages), the path terminates with the same red sphere indicating an unreachable frontier due to high semantic risk.

This result visually demonstrates how the traversability analysis whether based on geometric risk factors or semantic terrain understanding is seamlessly integrated into the STAGE global planning pipeline. By feeding traversability scores into the planner, the robot not only avoids unsafe regions but also flags unreachable areas during exploration. This enhances the reliability of the autonomy system when navigating unknown or changing underground environments.

Figure 2 showcases real-world results of the STAGE navigation system operating in a mine-like environment and highlights two challenging navigation cases:

- 1. Hazard Detection (Left Column, Top & Bottom - subfigures a, b):**
Subfigures (a) and (b) illustrate a scenario where the robot encounters a staircase inside a tunnel. Subfigure (a) presents the geometric traversability map of the scene, where the staircase area is rendered in red, denoting highly untraversable terrain. The robot's path planning system, driven by STAGE, generates a path (visualized with a blue/cyan and later pink/magenta line) that initially proceeds toward the staircase but halts just before the hazardous region. The final node is marked with a red sphere, indicating a non-traversable frontier, where exploration must stop. Subfigure (b) overlays the same path on a colored LiDAR point cloud, emphasizing surface details. This illustrates the robot's decision-making based on both traversability estimation and its semantic awareness of obstacles. The scene visually confirms how the robot correctly identifies the stairs as a traversal boundary, which aligns with its geometric safety constraints.

Figure 2: Examples of traversability-based decision-making by the STAGE navigation system in two mine tunnel scenarios. (a–b) A staircase hazard is detected using geometric (a) and colored point cloud (b) representations, leading the robot to stop exploration at a non-traversable frontier (red sphere). (c) Camera view of the staircase confirms the obstacle. (d–e) A flat and open junction area is analyzed using geometric (d) and semantic (e) traversability maps, both indicating safe terrain (green). (f) Camera image of the junction validates the mapping and terrain classification. These cases highlight STAGE's ability to assess terrain risks and autonomously decide whether to proceed or halt based on traversability information.

- 2. Junction Exploration and Terrain Assessment (Right Column, subfigures d, e, f):** Subfigures (d) and (e) demonstrate the robot's perception of a flat open junction or corridor area. Subfigure (d) shows the geometric traversability map, while subfigure (e) displays the corresponding semantic traversability map, both highlighting a wide, green zone that is safe for navigation. The scene is structured with voxelized representations indicating open traversable space with minimal surface irregularity. This supports confident forward navigation and future revisits to this region. Subfigure (f) offers the real camera image of the same corridor, validating the LiDAR-based map's accuracy. Similarly, subfigure (c) complements the earlier case with a ground truth image of the staircase location shown in (a).

Together, these examples illustrate how the robot can robustly:

- Detect and halt at hazardous obstacles like staircases.
- Safely explore and assess larger navigable areas such as junctions.
- Fuse geometry, semantics, and visual perception to make informed decisions about movement and map updates.

3.2 Environment Agonistic Semantic Traversability analysis.

In robotic navigation, it is a common practice to rely heavily on geometric features of the environment. Typically, navigation systems use registered geometric information such as point clouds or maps to determine viable paths. However, in most implementations, this geometric data does not incorporate additional

context about the environment, such as the type of surface or the nature of obstacles present. This omission can be problematic, particularly in unstructured or complex environments where geometric cues alone may be insufficient for ensuring safe and reliable navigation.

Unstructured environments pose significant challenges for geometry-based navigation strategies. These environments often contain irregular features, dynamic obstacles, and ambiguous terrain, where simple geometric representations may fail to capture critical aspects of traversability. For instance, transparent obstacles such as glass panels or wire mesh may be nearly invisible to depth sensors, leading to potential collisions. Similarly, surfaces like water, mud, or sand may appear geometrically flat but could be hazardous or entirely untraversable depending on the robotic platform's capabilities.

These challenges underscore the necessity for robotic systems to interpret and understand their surroundings at a more semantic level. A more robust understanding of the environment involves assessing not only the shape and layout of the terrain but also its meaning and suitability for traversal. This leads to the concept of traversability estimation, which focuses on evaluating regions of the environment in terms of their navigability, considering both geometric and semantic information.

Semantic segmentation refers to the process of assigning a class label to every pixel in an image. This technique enables the identification of various elements within a scene, such as roads, buildings, vegetation, and obstacles. However, semantic segmentation does not distinguish between separate instances of the same class for example, multiple trees are all labeled as "tree" without differentiating among them.

Among the many approaches used for semantic segmentation, deep learning methods have gained significant traction due to their impressive performance in real-world scenarios. A particularly effective category within these methods includes encoder-decoder architectures, which are designed to compress image features and then reconstruct them into detailed segmentation maps. Well-known examples of such models include Fully Convolutional Networks (FCN), SegNet, the High-Resolution Network (HRNet), V-Net, and U-Net. Each of these models follows the core idea of encoding contextual information through down sampling and then decoding to recover spatial details for accurate pixel-wise classification.

Another set of popular models relies on pyramid-based pooling strategies. These include networks like the Feature Pyramid Network (FPN), the Pyramid Scene Parsing Network (PSPNet), and DeepLabV3. These architectures aim to improve performance by capturing features at multiple scales, which helps the model better handle scenes with varying object sizes and spatial complexities.

In our approach, we use a semantic segmentation model based on MobileNetV3-Large combined with a lightweight encoder-decoder architecture known as LR-

ASPP. This model was selected primarily for its efficiency and real-time capability, making it suitable for deployment on resource-constrained robotic systems.

MobileNetV3 builds on the strengths of earlier versions by incorporating depth wise separable convolutions a method that separates spatial filtering and feature combining into two distinct operations. This significantly reduces both the computational load and the number of parameters, without compromising the model's ability to learn rich feature representations.

Two major enhancements were introduced in the third iteration of MobileNet. First, the initial and final layers of the network were redesigned to be more computationally efficient. Second, a new activation function, h-swish, was introduced. This function is a streamlined version of the original swish activation and offers advantages such as faster computation and better compatibility with quantization techniques, making it more suitable for embedded systems and real-time applications.

As part of the segmentation task, the terrain is categorized into six distinct classes, which are defined to support navigation in diverse environments. These classes are:

1. Background: Elements that are largely irrelevant to the navigation task, such as the sky or distant scenery.
2. Obstacle: Objects that are considered impassable for the robot. These include static structures and dynamic entities such as walls, furniture, vehicles, pedestrians, and trees.
3. Risky: Terrains that pose a significant hazard due to their unstable or dangerous nature, such as water, mud, or icy surfaces.
4. Rough: Traversable surfaces that may hinder motion or reduce efficiency, including gravel, sand, and uneven terrain.
5. Coarse: Areas that can be traversed but are generally avoided unless necessary. Examples include grass and loose dirt.
6. Flat: Smooth, even surfaces intended for traversal. This includes paved roads, indoor flooring, sidewalks, and similar infrastructure.

This classification enables a robot to make more informed decisions when planning paths, allowing it to avoid dangerous or suboptimal routes and favor more navigable terrain.

Figure 3: Overall framework architecture for traversability estimation.

Figure 4: Results of the traversed path in a dense forest environment.

Figure 5: Results of the traversed path in a snowy forest environment.

Figure 6: Results of the traversed path in a canopy forest environment.

Figure 7: Results of the traversed path in a subterranean tunnel environment.

Figure 8: Results of the traversed path in a room with a pile of gravel.

Figure 9: Results of the traversed path in a subterranean tunnel environment.

3.3 VLM-based traversable ground estimation directly from the RGB and LiDAR data.

Semantic segmentation is the task of assigning a class label to each pixel in an image, such that all pixels corresponding to the same semantic category (e.g., road, person, tree) receive the same label. The objective is to produce a dense, pixel-level classification that partitions the image into semantically meaningful regions. This task differs from image classification and object detection by requiring a comprehensive understanding of the spatial structure and context within the image. Semantic segmentation is essential for applications where detailed scene understanding is critical, such as autonomous navigation, medical image analysis, and robotic perception. It serves as a foundational component in systems that must interpret complex visual environments at a fine-grained level.

However, traversability estimation in unstructured environments presents unique challenges. Unlike structured settings such as indoor navigation or paved roads, unstructured environments such as forests, rocky terrain, or disaster zones exhibit high variability in surface textures, lighting conditions, occlusions, and the types of obstacles present. This variability makes it difficult for traditional supervised learning methods to generalize effectively. Moreover, semantic cues alone may be insufficient without contextual understanding of terrain characteristics (e.g., differentiating between grass that can be walked on versus tall bushes that block passage). These scenarios require models that can infer

semantics from sparse or ambiguous visual features and integrate contextual priors, making the case for more expressive and adaptable architectures.

Visual-language models (VLMs) bring significant advantages to robotic perception tasks. By aligning visual features with language embeddings, these models enable zero-shot learning the ability to recognize and segment novel concepts based on textual descriptions alone. This reduces the dependence on large, labeled datasets and provides a natural interface for human-robot interaction, where tasks can be specified via descriptive language. Additionally, VLMs enhance the semantic understanding of scenes, allowing robots to reason about their surroundings in more abstract or goal-oriented terms, such as identifying "navigable terrain" or "obstacles likely to be moved."

To perform semantic segmentation, the CLIPSeg model was employed, a transformer-based model trained on paired image-text data, leveraging its capability to segment images based on natural language prompts. CLIPSeg was chosen specifically due to its lightweight architecture and its effectiveness in performing prompt-based segmentation without needing class-specific training. Compared to other VLM-based segmentation models, CLIPSeg strikes a balance between accuracy, speed, and computational efficiency, making it well-suited for real-time perception tasks in robotic systems operating under uncertainty and variability.

Figure 10 : Zero-shot semantic segmentation based on CLIPSeg.

The process was designed to be modular and efficient, enabling integration into robotic perception systems. CLIPSeg was loaded using pre-trained weights. This model accepts an RGB image and a text prompt and outputs a segmentation mask highlighting regions in the image corresponding to the prompt. This allowed segmentation of semantically relevant regions based on human-interpretable descriptions (e.g., "traversable"). The pipeline can handle a live video stream or a static dataset. The steps for processing each image were as follows:

1. Input Acquisition and Preparation:

- A set of natural language prompts is entered (e.g., "traversable"), separated by commas.
- The selected image is read using OpenCV and converted from BGR (OpenCV default) to RGB format for compatibility with the CLIPSeg model.

2. Prompt and Image Preprocessing:

- For each prompt, the CLIPSeg processor prepares the image and text inputs:
 - The image is resized and normalized to match the model's expected input format.
 - The text prompts are tokenized and transformed into embeddings that can be interpreted by the transformer model.
 - Each prompt-image pair is stacked into a batch (one for each prompt), allowing parallel processing of multiple semantic concepts.

3. Model Inference:

- The pre-trained CLIPSeg model (CIDAS/clipseg-rd64-refined) performs inference on the batch of inputs.
- The model outputs a set of *logit maps*, where each map corresponds to the predicted relevance of pixels to a specific prompt.
- A sigmoid activation is applied to convert logits to probabilities, producing soft masks that represent per-pixel likelihoods.

4. Multi-Prompt Fusion:

- If multiple prompts are used, the corresponding soft masks are *combined multiplicatively* (i.e., via element-wise product). This ensures that only regions satisfying all prompt conditions are emphasized, which can be useful for refining specificity (e.g., "traversable" AND "flat").
- If a single prompt is used, its mask is directly used as the prediction.

5. Postprocessing and Visualization:

- The resulting soft mask is resized back to the original image dimensions.
- A colormap (e.g., *magma*) is applied to the soft mask to create a visually interpretable heatmap.
- This heatmap is then overlaid onto the original image using alpha blending, creating a composite that visually highlights the segmented regions.
- The name of the prompt(s) is annotated onto the image for clarity.

Figure 11: Traversability Segmentations. The traversable pixels are overlaid on the RGB stream of the on board camera.

CLIPSeg was chosen for its ability to generalize to unseen classes using zero-shot learning. This eliminated the need for class-specific training and allowed rapid adaptation to new environments and tasks. To maintain real-time performance:

- Inference was accelerated using GPU hardware.
- Batching and asynchronous processing techniques were employed when handling continuous image streams.

3.4 Risk assessment through routine scanning of the mining area.

Risk management standards in the mining industry are evaluated considering human safety, machinery integrity and environmental impact. The most significant risk is the potential loss of life and the health of individuals involved in the mining process, as well as the well-being of residents living near the mining area (environmental impact). Additionally, the safety of machinery and equipment used in mining, along with the accuracy of the mining process, are important considerations (Tubis et al. 2020).

Routine scanning is essential for identifying risky areas in underground mining due to the influence of multiple factors. Mining areas are dynamic environments; as material is extracted, the surrounding rock mass shifts. Furthermore, the extraction of resources can lead to negative impacts like surface subsidence, aquifer breakage, and land degradation (Du Z. et al. 2023, Bayirli M. et al. 2013). Specifically, as materials are removed, the shifting masses contribute to formatting new structures. Routine scanning is crucial for capturing these topological changes in 3D, as it provides vital information to mining personnel. Specifically, they can compare current and previous scans and stay informed about the evolving structure of the mined area (Temkin I. 2021).

Collapse hazard detection includes methods that predict rockfalls, roof collapses and wall failures. In general, the likelihood of roof fall hazard occurrence is directly related to the local geology, the presence of horizontal stresses as well as the type of excavation method and the efficacy of the roof support system in use. Due to the complexity of this process, it is important to continuously assess the risk of roof falls - especially in long life-term work areas where mining crews are frequently present. Subtle signs, such as rock bulging or fracture widening are important indicators that may precede such events. (Fuławka K., 2022). As a result, frequent scanning plays a key role in the early detection of these changes, enabling preventive action before damage expands -thereby improving safety and reducing downtime.

Routine scanning provides real data on stress concentrations or zones with unusual deformation. As a result, mining operations can prioritize reinforcement or proactively evacuate high-risk areas. Risk assessment is conducted using a combination of methods that grade risks based on their probability of occurrence and severity, presented in a simple format that is understandable to all workers. This information is essential for risk-based decision-making (Rudakov M., 2021)

Frequent data updates support predictive modeling and the development of accurate, relevant geotechnical models. Ultimately, routine scanning helps eliminate the need for spot-checks and fosters a culture of continuous monitoring.

To create realistic conditions where risk assessment is needed, changes were made to the simulation environment of the abandoned mine. More specifically, three variations of the mine were created. The first one includes rockfalls that

completely block part of a tunnel of the mine and make it impossible for the mining machine used in the simulation to traverse through or around it.

Figure 12 Blocked tunnel of the abandoned mine from rockfall in the simulated environment.

The second variation contains a partially deformed part of the tunnel of the abandoned mine where the ceiling is lowered, and the overall cross section has been reduced. It is significantly harder for the ground vehicle to traverse.

Figure 13 The deformed tunnel in the second variant of the mine (left) and the same tunnel in the original simulated environment (right). With the red arrows the part of the ceiling that has been lowered can be observed while the blue arrows indicate the difference in the width between the two versions.

The third variation contains a partially deformed part of the tunnel in the same manner as in the second variation while it includes the addition of rockfall that partially blocks the tunnel.

Figure 14 Depiction of the third variant of the simulated environment that contains rockfalls and deformities (left). Depiction of the same part of the mine in the original simulated environment (right).

After creating the variations of the simulated environments multiple simulations were conducted. In the simulations the mining machine, firstly, navigates through the variant of the environment of the mine that does not contain any rockfalls or deformities to create point cloud maps of the mine using LiDAR and IMU SLAM algorithms such as DLIO. Then, additional simulations are conducted where the mining machine must traverse again from the same areas of the mine it while contains rockfalls and deformities. These maps are utilized in Section 3.9 where the changes between the first point clouds that were created in the original mine environment are compared to the new point clouds that include the changes in the areas of the mine.

Figure 15 Pointcloud map created by the mining machine. On the top picture (red pointcloud) the ceiling of the tunnel is deformed. On the bottom picture (yellow pointcloud) the same area is depicted as it was mapped in the original simulated environment.

3.5 Change detection based on latest map with respect to past point cloud map.

Task 4.3 focuses on the development of a method to detect temporal changes in underground environments by comparing sequential 3D point cloud (PCD) maps. The objective is to automatically identify structural alterations, such as rockfalls, tunnel deformation, or newly introduced obstructions, by analyzing deviations between scans captured at different time instances.

The core motivation for this task lies in the need to monitor underground environments that evolve gradually due to excavation-induced stress, environmental conditions, or natural degradation. Such changes can signify emerging hazards and are often difficult to detect through single-pass observation. By aligning and comparing historical and current PCD maps, Task 4.3 enables the detection of localized geometric anomalies that may indicate collapse-prone regions or restricted access zones.

This capability is tightly coupled to routine inspection procedures; wherein autonomous robotic platforms perform scheduled mapping runs through previously scanned areas. By leveraging these repeated scans, the change detection framework supports ongoing structural assessment as part of a

continuous risk management cycle. In doing so, it shifts the paradigm from reactive inspection to predictive monitoring, where early signs of instability can be identified before they escalate into operational hazards.

The approach also aligns with broader safety standards in mining, where the timely identification of deformation or obstruction is essential for minimizing risk to personnel and equipment. Simulated test scenarios provided by UPAT, featuring altered tunnel geometry and induced collapses, serve as benchmarks to evaluate the method's ability to highlight affected regions and support downstream risk-aware navigation.

Method Overview:

The change detection method developed in Task 4.3 is specifically designed to support routine inspection workflows in underground environments, where an autonomous robot navigates through previously explored areas on a scheduled basis. Recognizing that the robot may follow slightly different trajectories across successive inspection passes, the method does not require exact scan-to-scan overlap but instead relies on learned global descriptors and map-level alignment to ensure comparability.

The pipeline, also depicted, operates on bi-temporal 3D point cloud maps, captured at two different time instances, and consists of three main stages:

Map Alignment:

To account for natural deviations in the robot's pose and path, both scans are aligned into a common global frame using the map-merging framework described in D4.4. This component computes a rigid transformation based on the spatial and topological consistency between the two maps, ensuring that all subsequent comparisons operate in a shared reference system. This step is critical for enabling map-to-map consistency across non-identical trajectories.

Change Region Localization via Descriptor Comparison:

Instead of relying on direct point-wise matching which might not scale well for large areas, the method employs place recognition descriptors, compact, learned representations of spatial segments. These descriptors are recorded during mapping and enable efficient retrieval of regions with high dissimilarity between scans. By querying the two descriptor sets against each other, the method identifies areas that have changed the most in terms of structural appearance, while tolerating minor positional offsets between trajectories.

Irregular Object Extraction via Point-to-Voxel Comparison:

For each detected change region, spherical submaps are extracted and compared using a voxelized occupancy check. Points from the newer scan that fall outside the voxel grid defined by the earlier scan are flagged as potentially new or

displaced objects. This approach effectively identifies local deformations, added obstacles, or collapsed material. A statistical filtering step is then applied to eliminate isolated outliers and retain only coherent structural changes.

Figure 16 : The overall change detection and object extraction pipeline of the proposed solution. The robot r explores or navigates through the same area in two different time instances, t and $t + 1$, while simultaneously collecting descriptors in a stack Q from the point clouds P . After aligning both maps M_t and M_{t+1} to the common map frame W^G , the changed areas S_{ki} and S_{kj} are detected using the place recognition descriptors Q_t and Q_{t+1} and then within those areas the objects are extracted by a point-to-voxel comparison.

Evaluation Setup

To evaluate the proposed change detection method under controlled but realistic conditions, a series of test scenarios were created by UPAT using the simulated underground mining environment. The simulation was designed to replicate typical challenges encountered during routine robotic inspection, such as tunnel deformation, debris accumulation, and blockage of passages.

Three evaluation scenarios were generated by varying the structure and contents of the mine while maintaining a common base map for comparison:

- **Normal (Reference) Map:** This map represents the undisturbed state of the environment and serves as the reference scan against which all others are compared. It models an intact tunnel layout with no deformations or obstructions, simulating the initial condition after a full inspection and mapping pass.

Figure 17: 3D point cloud map provided by UPAT, serving as a reference for detecting changes and identifying potential risks when compared to maps from subsequent missions.

- **Scenario 2: Deformed Tunnel Walls:** In this scenario, localized deformations were introduced into the tunnel geometry, such as wall bulging and roof deflection, to emulate the types of subtle structural changes that may precede collapse. These deformations are difficult to detect visually or from isolated metrics, making them ideal for validating the change detection pipeline.

Figure 18 : 3D point cloud illustrating tunnel deformation.

- **Scenario 3: Added Debris (Rockfall Obstruction):** This case builds on Scenario 2 by adding scattered rock debris and loose material to the tunnel floor, simulating a partial rockfall event. While the tunnel remains passable, the presence of new objects and occluded surfaces challenges the system's ability to isolate irregular additions from geometric deformation.

Figure 19 : 3D point cloud illustrating tunnel deformation and locations of rockfalls within the tunnel.

- **Scenario 4: Blocked Entrance (Severe Obstruction):** The final scenario simulates a more critical condition in which the tunnel entrance is obstructed by a collapsed segment or displaced material. This poses a significant navigation hazard and serves as a stress test for the pipeline's capacity to detect large-scale structural change and inaccessible regions.

Figure 20 : 3D point cloud illustrating a partially blocked tunnel entrance.

Each scenario is evaluated by comparing its point cloud map to the original reference map using the developed change detection method. The goal is to assess whether the system can successfully extract and highlight the altered structures or objects that caused the change. Together, these test cases span a range of structural conditions that may arise in real mine operations, providing a representative benchmark for validating the pipeline's effectiveness in routine risk-aware inspection scenarios.

Results from Simulation Environment:

The developed change detection pipeline was evaluated using the three simulation-based scenarios provided by UPAT. These scenarios were specifically designed to test the system's sensitivity to structural deformation, object addition, and large-scale occlusions. The evaluation begins with the comparison between the reference map and the deformed tunnel map.

Deformed Tunnel

In this case, subtle geometric changes were introduced to the tunnel walls to simulate realistic structural deformation. As shown in the accompanying figures, the initial alignment step was successful in registering the deformed map to the original coordinate frame. Even at this stage, some of the deformation is visually discernible, providing a consistent spatial basis for change detection.

Figure 21 : Aligned reference and deformed 3D point cloud maps, highlighting areas of partial deformation.

Following alignment, the pipeline performs its bi-temporal analysis and outputs two types of detected changes:

- Green-highlighted points represent parts of the map that no longer exist in the new scan, i.e., material or structure that has been displaced or deformed away.
- Red-highlighted points indicate newly introduced geometry, such as expanded bulges or newly visible surfaces caused by the deformation.

Figure 22 : Result of the change detection pipeline. Green points indicate points removed from the reference map, while red points represent newly added points. Visible deformations are highlighted.

This dual-labeling scheme allows for an intuitive understanding of directional change: not just that change occurred, but how the structure evolved (removed vs. added material). As illustrated in the figures, the system effectively localizes these changes along the altered tunnel sections and distinguishes between retained and newly appearing geometry.

Despite the sparse resolution of the simulated LiDAR scans and the use of conservative filtering to reduce noise, the system was able to detect meaningful deformations. Some fine-scale changes may be partially filtered, while occasional outliers persist, especially in low-density regions or near edges. These are expected limitations under current data fidelity, and will be addressed in future work by:

- Incorporating denser point clouds,
- Exploring adaptive voxel filtering strategies,
- And employing local surface fitting or confidence-based pruning.

A closer inspection of the point cloud maps shows visible changes in tunnel cross-section, confirming that the proposed method captures real geometric variance, not just noise artifacts. This is particularly promising for use cases where early detection of tunnel expansion, collapse precursors, or instability indicators is critical for operational safety.

Figure 23 : Detailed view of tunnel deformation highlighting red points identified by the change detection pipeline as additions compared to the reference map. Some outliers are present, attributed to mapping inaccuracies and partial sparsity of the map.

Deformed Tunnel and Rockfall

The second scenario introduces scattered rockfall debris into the tunnel, simulating a partial obstruction event. In this case, the topology remains largely similar to the original, but localized accumulations of material on the tunnel floor new navigation hazards.

Figure 24 : Visualization of the deformed tunnel, highlighting newly detected areas in red. Deformation is clearly visible towards the front, while rockfalls are observed further back.

After map alignment, the change detection framework identifies multiple small-volume changes concentrated towards the deformed portion of the tunnel. As in the previous scenario, the output highlights red regions where new material, such as rock clusters, has been introduced.

As shown in the figures, the red points accurately correspond to the locations of added debris, while the green regions are sparser—indicating areas where previously observed surfaces are now occluded by the new material. This distinction is critical, as it allows inspection systems to distinguish between true object addition and line-of-sight occlusion, both of which are relevant for risk assessment.

Figure 25 : Close-up view of tunnel deformation and rockfalls, with affected areas highlighted in red.

The system demonstrates good precision in identifying small but dense clusters of change, even when the surrounding structure remains unchanged. This is particularly important for operational scenarios where unexpected obstructions, such as minor rockfalls, may not significantly deform the tunnel geometry but can still impede robotic navigation or present physical hazards to human crews.

Some residual noise remains in areas near the boundary of the debris clusters, where sparse point coverage or marginal voxel occupancy can lead to ambiguous classification. However, the overall quality of detection remains consistent, and the performance is robust to these limitations.

This scenario validates the pipeline's sensitivity to localized topological additions and highlights its potential for monitoring obstruction growth over time. The method's ability to isolate even small-scale changes supports its use for early

hazard detection and contributes to informed navigation or rerouting decisions within an autonomous inspection loop.

Blocked Entrance

The final evaluation scenario simulates a severe event in which the tunnel entrance is obstructed by large boulders, representing a full collapse or significant debris accumulation. This condition prevents the robot from accessing or mapping the tunnel beyond a certain point, effectively truncating the scan and occluding previously visible regions.

Following the alignment of the reference map and the obstructed map, the framework accurately identifies a large region of removed points beyond the point of collapse, highlighted in green. These represent structural areas that were visible in the original scan but are now absent due to the robot's inability to proceed past the blockage. This removed region serves as an implicit indicator of occlusion or inaccessibility.

Figure 26 : Visualization of the blocked tunnel entrance. Red points indicate new blockage areas absent in the reference map, while green points represent areas removed from visibility due to obstruction during mapping.

In parallel, partial boulder geometry at the point of collapse is detected and highlighted in red, corresponding to newly observed surfaces not present in the reference map.

Figure 27 : Detailed view highlighting changes in the reference map caused by the blockage.

This combination of red and green regions effectively communicates both:

- The presence of a physical blockage (via the added geometry), and
- The loss of previously mappable space (via the removed geometry).

Together, these two outputs capture the full impact of the collapse event both the structural addition (boulders) and the navigational consequence (lack of access beyond the obstruction). The system does not require prior knowledge of tunnel topology; it infers the hazard purely from observed deviations between routine scans.

While the internal structure of the blockage is only partially visible due to occlusion, the pipeline provides a strong, interpretable signal of critical change.

This makes it suitable for integration into automated hazard alerts, especially in remote inspection scenarios where human intervention may be delayed.

4 Partner Contributions

Task 4.3 is led by the LTU team, with a focus on integrating traversability analysis into the autonomous planning pipeline. LTU contributes by embedding real-time traversability assessment directly into the STAGE planner, enabling adaptive path planning based on terrain conditions. The team develops an environment-agnostic traversability estimation framework that operates on RGB-D camera data and is further enhanced with a VLM-based method for direct identification of traversable ground. This supports safe and robust navigation across diverse and unstructured underground environments.

The University of Patras (UPAT) team contributes by executing repeated simulations in environments with and without tunnel deformation. These simulations generate point cloud (PCD) maps that reflect both nominal and altered terrain conditions. LTU uses this dataset to perform change detection analysis, enabling identification of deformation zones that may pose structural risks or potential collapse. This collaborative approach supports the development of proactive risk-aware navigation strategies for underground exploration. EPI team has given valuable feedback on risk assessment and finding risk prone zones within a mining environment through routine scanning. The discussion has helped understand the requirements from a mining machine supplier prospective to have repeatable automated routine scanning for risk assessment.

5 Future Plans

As part of the continued work related to Task 4.3, the upcoming field trial in September 2025 at the GM mine in Athens will play a key role in further validating and strengthening the traversability estimation and risk assessment methods developed thus far. During this field deployment, we plan to collect real-world terrain and perception data under operational conditions, which will provide critical input for refining and stress-testing the algorithms. This data collection effort will help verify the generalizability of our terrain analysis and risk modeling approaches across diverse underground settings and sensor conditions. It will also support parameter tuning, model retraining, and edge-case evaluation that are difficult to replicate in simulation environments alone.

The insights gained from this field trial will directly contribute to the next phase of the project within Work Package 5 (WP5), which focuses on system integration and experimental validation. The goal is to transition the current pipeline—originally tested under simulated conditions using ground-truth odometry—toward fully autonomous terrain reasoning based on onboard perception and SLAM outputs, as established in Task 4.4. This will enable robust risk-aware planning and decision-making in the absence of external localization infrastructure. Ultimately, these efforts aim to bring the traversability estimation framework to a level of maturity suitable for real-world deployment in dynamic, unstructured, and safety-critical underground environments.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable detailed a comprehensive framework for terrain traversability estimation and risk assessment in underground mining environments, forming a core part of Task 4.3. Through the integration of geometric and semantic analysis techniques, as well as RGB-LiDAR data fusion, the presented methods allow autonomous machines to evaluate terrain safety in real time using only onboard sensors. Additionally, risk was assessed not only in the moment but over time, through the implementation of change detection and repeated environment scanning. This enables the system to adapt to dynamic and potentially degraded environments an essential capability for safe autonomous operation in subterranean spaces. These methods have been successfully tested in simulation and prepared for future deployment. Their integration into the broader STAGE autonomy stack ensures that they can contribute meaningfully to multi-agent exploration and decision-making. The outcomes of this task set the stage for experimental validation during the upcoming field trial and full-system integration under WP5.

7 References

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